

INTRODUCTION

The relevance relates to the rapid development of technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing, and automation that characterize the digital economy. Digitalization affects all areas of life, including education, healthcare, and public administration. Adapting the workforce in these areas is essential to utilize new technologies and improve services effectively.

Employers are now looking for professionals with technical skills and the ability to think critically and be creative and adaptable. Companies that successfully adapt their employees to digital change can innovate faster and achieve sustainable development, which is critical in a globally competitive environment.

Thus, the issues of training and adaptation of qualified personnel in the digital economy are topical and require attention from businesses, educational institutions, and government agencies.

Literature review

Innovations and technological developments have laid the foundations for an economy based on digital goods and services – the digital economy which became an integral part of the global economy.

As J. A. Audestad et al. writes, the existence of the digital economy depends entirely on the evolution of information and communication technology (ICT) which started in the 1950s, creating some of the largest companies in the world, and is ongoing [1].

To remain competitive in global education, universities focus on digital transformation strategies.

M. Hashim et al. writes that scientific approaches to the development and design of transformation models will make it easier and more effective for university leaders to implement this process without losing resources. The authors point out the necessity and effectiveness of using a sustainable plan in designing, developing, and implementing university digital transformation projects [2].

S. Taranukha et al. consider transforming the electronic information and educational environment of a transportation university into a digital ecosystem based on AI technologies [3].

Digital literacy and competence have become key skills in the digital economy; these include effectively using digital technologies, tools, and resources to solve various tasks.

A. Bacalja et al. argue that preparing young people for digital citizenship should emphasize critical digital literacies that align with current digital development trends and digital technologies that have not yet penetrated formal school education [4].

L. Dorohan-Pisarenko et al. identified the essence, approaches, and tools for developing and measuring digital competence of economics students [5].

K. Tzafilkou et al. believe that assessing students' digital competence levels and designing educational programs for their development are of paramount importance. The authors propose a comprehensive digital competence scale for university students; this instrument includes skills in online learning and collaboration, social media, smart and mobile devices, security, and data protection [6].

P. Lypez Vicent et al. examined competence as personal information management skills among undergraduate students in Spanish universities. The results showed that students have positive self-esteem regarding their competence in personal information management. However, they do not take advantage of all the opportunities the digital world offers them [7].

Digital ergonomics plays a vital role in the digital economy, creating user-friendly and efficient interfaces that improve user interaction with technology.

Z. C. Eldho & K. Muthukumar note that students often do not realize the importance of ergonomics, particularly the rules for working on computers and mobile devices. The authors aim to help students determine the level of risk of sitting in an uncomfortable posture during their online studies. Some ergonomic tips are provided to help online students avoid bad habits and fatigue when working on phones, tablets, laptops, and desktops [8].

S. Schlund et al. write that digital ergonomics tools promote competitiveness through perspective-taking. The authors believe that firmly anchoring the topic of digital ergonomics in relevant subjects of university studies is a prerequisite for the preparation of competitive graduates [9].

Entrepreneurship among students in the digital economy is becoming an increasingly common and important phenomenon. This is due to various factors, including availability of technology, support of educational institutions, and the growing interest of young people in creating their businesses.

R. Singh et al. write that technological advances motivate students to become potential entrepreneurs. The author's study showed that optimism and realism significantly influence business opportunities of future entrepreneurs [10].

Thus, the scientific problem of adapting qualified personnel in the digital economy is the need for a deep understanding and analysis of the processes associated with changes

in skill requirements, as well as mechanisms that contribute to successful adaptation of workers to new conditions.

It is necessary to analyze the current and future needs of employers in qualified personnel and identify gaps between supply and demand in the labor market.

New human resource management strategies that consider the digital economy peculiarities need to be developed, such as remote work, flexible schedules, and the use of digital platforms for interaction.

Educational programs need to be revised and updated to train professionals to meet the requirements of the digital economy. This includes technical and interpersonal, critical thinking, and creativity skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were articles on adaptation in the conditions of digitalization, theory of work organization, change management, and modern teaching methods published in periodicals: Education and Information Technologies, The Australian Journal of Language and Literacy, International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education, Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research, Zeitschrift für Arbeitswissenschaft, Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research and others.

Monographs and collections of articles on digital economy, human resource management, and educational technologies were also used.

Research methods: content analysis, analysis of publications, press releases, and company materials related to their HR adaptation strategies.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The rapidly developing digital economy affects various spheres of human activity in modern society, inevitably changing the educational environment. The digital economy is quite mobile; new professions appear quickly, and others that have lost their importance and relevance are abolished. Accordingly, the requirements for personnel training are also changing due to relatively rapid transformations.

Digitalization is one of the priority areas for the development of society and the education system in particular, which is clearly outlined in program documents and is comprehensively supported by the state. The priority national project 'Education' and the federal project 'Digital Educational Environment' are designed to change and improve the system of Russian education to introduce and ensure the effectiveness of using the latest digital technologies in the learning process [11].

Digitalization inevitably changes the population's employment structure and the educational environment as a supplier of personnel who will work in entirely different conditions. Given the high mobility and variability of the current situation both in the geopolitical and economic life of the country and in higher education, there is a need to study the socio-psychological adaptation of students, taking into account the ongoing changes. At the same time, taking into account the speed of the ongoing changes, it is rather difficult to assess the range of challenges and problems that the sphere of higher education is facing.

Thus, there is a rapid growth trend in the number of information technology students in all areas of education, from primary to postgraduate, all over the world. Disputes among scientists about the benefits, harms, and effectiveness of using new educational technologies in the educational process continue, especially among parents of schoolchildren. Still, one thing is undeniable – they have a great future connected with informatization and digitalization of all spheres of life worldwide [12].

A person becomes not a central measurement of civilization but the leading spiritual, moral, and intellectual standard. The pace and nature of the transformation of the social sphere actualize the problems of comprehension of adaptation mechanisms and the need to understand and anticipate the results of globalization. Social transformations have increased human interest in the search for modern tools to manage communication and revealed the need to study the peculiarities of the impact of information and new media on human orientational values and ideals, and adaptation [13].

The problem of students' socialization in modern society is determined by the peculiarities of social and spiritual-moral development of the state, globalization of all processes in the world space, on the one hand, and individualization of personality, on the other hand, devaluation of moral and ethical ideals in public consciousness for a long time, the loss of certain genuine value orientations by young people, the prevalence of pragmatic views. Social and psychological adaptation of students is also significant in the professional formation of highly qualified specialists, as it directly affects the success of their training, the formation of

professional competencies, and social productivity. On this basis, it is necessary to understand the main directions of development in higher education, as personnel training is one of the most critical components of the economy's digitalization.

This problem was especially acute for first-year students in 2020 due to the transition of universities to distance learning due to the pandemic [14]. Students' social and psychological adaptation took place in difficult socio-psychological conditions due to limited opportunities for communication with classmates and the need to apply self-management in distance learning [15].

It is well known that various students, entering university, find themselves in new conditions, as they come from the regions to megacities where the way of life, value orientations, and subcultures of young people are entirely different. They face various difficulties in adaptation from the first days of study: gaining authority among fellow students, establishing interpersonal relations, and being included in new reference groups. Students from the regions also have to solve other social and domestic difficulties: adaptation to an independent life, the need to cope with household problems without the help of parents, keeping a budget, etc. Thus, adaptation of first-year students takes place at all levels: economic, social, psychological, physiological, and academic.

Metropolitan youth, especially in good-level universities, are plagued by a hedonistic lifestyle foreign to visiting students, which usually leads to misunderstandings and conflicts. Students may be advised to exercise or read books to alleviate symptoms, yet most prefer to party with alcohol and tobacco products, which is nothing more than everyday escapism and thus not a solution.

For numerous students, life away from parents and old friends causes existential fear and panic which is a normal reaction of the limbic system of the human organism to a fundamentally new environment and the absence of "others" in the identification of "one's own – another's." In most cases, this fear is reinforced by the novelty and strangeness of what is happening, which means that forming the habit of independent living will help solve the problem of the new student's non-adaptability to the new normality. With the search for friends, everything is a little more difficult in the 1st year, precisely because of the circumstances mentioned above, but do not forget that there is a possibility of uniting students based on non-acceptance of norms and morals professed by other students.

Quick and, most importantly, qualitative adaptation to a new environment is critical for a student. Labor productivity and the amount of information assimilated depend on it. The

university's task is to help its students discover their adaptive capabilities and abilities to achieve goals in a complex changing world in the digital economy.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Every year, digitalization covers more and more areas of activity, which requires new skills and knowledge from workers. This creates a constant demand for research and development in workforce adaptation.

Transition to the digital economy requires revising educational standards and programs. This opens up opportunities for creating new academic initiatives, courses, and professional development programs, which can be the subject of scientific research.

Developing and implementing new human resource management practices, such as flexible schedules, remote work, and digital platforms, create new challenges and research opportunities. Studying the impact of digitalization on motivation, job satisfaction, and employee professional development opens up new areas for research in occupational psychology and sociology.

Rapid changes in skill requirements and occupations demand constant monitoring and analysis of the labor market, which creates a need for new research and data. Human resource adaptation in the digital economy requires integrating knowledge from different fields, such as economics, psychology, sociology, and management, which promotes interdisciplinary research.

Skill adaptation is becoming an important topic not only at the level of individual countries but also globally, and it opens up opportunities for international cooperation and the exchange of experiences.

Thus, the topic of adaptation of qualified personnel in the digital economy has promising prospects for further research and practical applications, which makes it relevant and significant in today's world.

REFERENCES

1. Øverby, H., & Audestad, J. A. (2021). The Digital Economy. In: Introduction to Digital Economics. Classroom Companion: Business. Springer, Cham.
2. Mohamed Hashim, M., Tlemsani, I., & Duncan Matthews, R. (2022). A sustainable

- university: Digital Transformation and Beyond. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27, 8961–8996.
3. Taranukha, S., Saveleva, M., & Fomina, I. (2022). Development of a Conceptual Model of the Digital Ecosystem of Students Based on the Transformation of the Electronic Information and Educational Environment of the Transport University. In: Manakov, A., Edigarian, A. (eds) International Scientific Siberian Transport Forum TransSiberia – 2021. Trans-Siberian 2021. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 402. Springer, Cham.
 4. Bacalja, A., Beavis, C. & O'Brien, A. (2022). Shifting landscapes of digital literacy. *The Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 45, 253–263.
 5. Dorohan-Pisarenko, L., Bezkrivnyi, O., Pryidak, T., Leha, O., Yaloveha, L., & Krasota, O. (2022). Designing a Tool for Economics Students Digital Competence Measurement. In: Ignatenko, O., et al. ICTERI 2021 Workshops. ICTERI 2021. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol. 1635. Springer, Cham
 6. Tzafilkou, K., Perifanou, M., & Economides, A. A. (2022). Development and validation of students' digital competence scale (SDiCoS). *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19, 30.
 7. Lypez Vicent, P., Serrano, J. L., & Gutiérrez Porlán, I. (2022). Personal Management of Digital Information in University Students from a Gender Perspective. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 11, 114–129.
 8. Eldho, Z. C., & Muthukumar, K. (2022). Ergonomic Risk Assessment of Students in Digital Learning. In: Siddiqui, N. A., Khan, F., Tauseef, S. M., Ghanem, W. S., Garaniya, V. (eds) Advances in Behavioral Based Safety. Springer, Singapore
 9. Schlund, S., Kamusella, C., Knott, V. et al. (2022). Digital ergonomics and digital work planning in university education: experiences from Germany and Austria. *Zeitschrift für Arbeitswissenschaft*, 76, 510–524.
 10. Singh, R., Dwivedi, A., Gupta, S. et al. (2022). Elucidating the moderating role of personality traits in probing the linkage between digital entrepreneurship characteristics and perceived opportunities. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 12, 175–188. National Project "Education". Available at: <https://edu.gov.ru/national-project> (date of reference: 11 February 2022).
 11. Hasanova Z.B. (2021). Role of electronic educational resources in pandemic conditions. *Innovative technologies in education*, 1(6), 54–60.
 12. Evseeva, L. I., & Evseev, V. V. (2017). The problem of human social adaptation in new

communicative environments. (St. Petersburg Peter the Great Polytechnic University, St. Petersburg, RF. *St. Petersburg Polytechnic University Journal. Humanities and social sciences*, 8 (2), 20–29. Available at: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/problema-sotsialnoy-adaptatsii-cheloveka-v-novyh-kommunikativnyh-sredah/viewer> (accessed 12 February 2022)

13. Soliman, C., Salman, D., & GamalEldin, G. O. (2022). Students' perceptions of online learning in higher education during COVID-19: an empirical study of MBA and DBA students in Egypt. *Future Business Journal*, 8, 45.
14. Krylova, N. P., Levashov, E. N. (2022). Attitude of University Students to the Information Content of Electronic Educational Platforms. *Scientific and Technical Information Processing*, 49, 180–190.

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